

TATSUBO

TATSUBO was founded in 1901 as a cotton weaving business, and has primarily focused on cotton spinning as its main industry

sliver

Unidirectional and easy impregnation

Experimental results

Test number	Vf(%)	Sheet Layer	Thickness (mm)
101	3.7	1	2
102	9.2	1	1
103	23.0	5	3.5

Unidirectional composites-tensile test

Test number	Strength (MPa)	Coefficient of Variation
101	126	0.120
102	235	0.136
103	355	0.155

Scatter of strength

Comparison between experimental results and calculation results from rule of mixture

Test number	Vf(%)	Elastic modulus (GPa) (Experimental value)	Elastic modulus (GPa) (Calculated value)	Strength (MPa) (Experimental value)	Strength (MPa) (Calculated value)
101	3.70	9.35	12.2	126	186
102	9.20	28.6	24.7	235	377
103	23.0	27.0	55.9	355	857

SEM

Support fabric can be seen at right side

Fiber aligned unidirectionally

Good impregnation state

Good interfacial properties

Conclusion

- Continuous fiber composite → spinning tech ✓
- Good impregnation state → sliver ✓
- Rule of mixture → approx 50% reduction ✓
- Scatter of strength → approx 15% ✓